

Rejuvenation of Water Bodies in Kerala-A Case Study of Kanampuzha River at Kannur District

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: November

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2319-961X

Impact Factor: 4.005

Citation:

T, Jjikumari.

“Rejuvenation of Water Bodies in Kerala-A Case Study of Kanampuzha River at Kannur District.”

Shanlax International Journal of Economics, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 70–73.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1488519>

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Abstract

Kerala, God's Own Country, blessed with a lot of water bodies including rivers, ponds, lakes streams, etc. Due to the higher density of population, excessive land use, indiscriminate resource extractions, and severe human intervention made this state as 'Devils Own Country' and became a graveyard due to natural calamities. To attain sustainable development, rejuvenation of water bodies plays an important role. For that, the government of Kerala adopted an ambitious project of Rejuvenation of water bodies in associating with Haritha Kerala Mission. It includes clearing up activities of stagnant water bodies including canals, rivers and local ponds. This paper aimed to make a case study of the revival of Kanampuzha River situated at Kannur district and trying to make more efforts to extend this programmes to nearby areas through public participation and make aware the public about the necessity of water conservation for sustainable development.

Keywords: Rejuvenation, sustainable development, Haritha Kerala Mission, Kanampuzha River.

Introduction

“Water is precious natural resources”, without this life will not exist in this universe. From history, we could understand that civilization developed around water bodies and it was utilized not only for consumption purpose but the development of agriculture and used as a means of transport. Nowadays, the discussion is going on about the quantity and quality of water. In the earlier periods, our forefathers recognize the quality of water through the sight, smell, and taste. Only after the development modern technologies to check the water quality, and its influence on health of living beings were identified. Only 0.01% of total water is fresh water existing in the earth's crust, and it is rich in turbidity, sand, and bacteria.

There are three factors are determining the quality of water in an area. They are the character, the catchment, the topography, and the nature of development by weather and seasonal changes. Underground water usually contains very little amount of organic and suspended matter but may contain a large amounts of minerals like sodium, potassium, iron, aluminum, manganese, sulfate, carbonate, bicarbonate, etc. Nowadays almost all developing and developed countries are facing the problem of water scarcity, and it is a very precious natural resource. According to the United Nations Foundation (2000), only 50% of 550 million people of Southeast Asia have access to safe drinking water. Most often the people in the rural area especially, in developing countries are using contaminated water drawn from public wells, lakes, and ponds for their

usual purposes. And this leads to alarming health problems. Serious ill-health caused by water - borne diseases is reported all around the world (Linda Nash, 1993). Globally 2.3 billion people suffer from water-related diseases (WHO, 1997). Contamination of water is happening in industrially developed countries due to the emission of chemicals and other waste from the industries to nearby water bodies. In developing countries, water is polluting mainly because of the untreated waste and effluents into it. Water with fecal contamination could contain enteric pathogens dangerous to health, and a total coliform group of organisms is the principal and reliable indicator, used to assess the microbiological quality of drinking water as far as fecal pollution is concerned (Evan, 1981). According to the World Commission on Water for the 21st century, majority of water bodies of the universe are so contaminated, and that may be poisonous to human health and whole ecosystem. Nowadays people are more aware about water pollution, and trying to find solutions for attainable, sustainable water management all over the world. Industrialization, urbanization, etc. create a lot of contamination towards waterbodies and want to find out the solution of the same. Increasing population and human made activities directly lead to pollution of water bodies through the increased emission of waters and other matters directly or indirectly to the water bodies.

Kerala is known as God's own country. The greenery, topographic uniqueness, and availability of abundant water, etc. are behind this belief. But the present situation of Kerala is not hopeful in case of availability of fresh water and many parts of Kerala are facing acute water shortage and also facing the problem of contamination of water. Regarding the total land area Kerala constitutes only 1.1 percent of the total area of India but having 3.5 per cent of population, and it is the small state in India having the highest population density. The mismatch between these two will reflect in the per capita availability of natural resources. During the seventies, most of our water bodies get damaged due to the waste from paper and pulp mills, fertilizer, and chemical factories, distilleries and food processing units without considering their environmental impacts and pollution problems. After that frequent waterborne diseases, and fish, damages are reported from such areas. There is an increase in complexity over water pollution problems due to the features of Kerala water bodies such as short length, lean flow during summer, backwater, tidal influence, and salinity, etc.

Kerala has 44 rivers among them three of them are east flowing rivers. But all of them starting from the Western Ghats and 41 rivers are draining towards the Arabian Sea, and three are draining towards nearby states like Karnataka and Tamil Nadu. Moreover, five major lakes are at southern Kerala and some backwaters also located in Coastal line.

Pollution and deterioration of water quality start from the settlement of man nearby water bodies onwards. But its consequences are experiencing recently. But due to industrial development and urbanization, this problem further increased in Kerala.

Water quality is essential not only drinking purpose but for agriculture, industrial, and other uses. Due to urbanization and industrialization, surface waters in rivers and lakes also facing threats. More over-dependence on underground water has grown over the past few decades, and its quality also shows a declining trend.

The Objective of the Study

To evaluate the rejuvenation activities of water bodies especially Kanampuzha River at Kannur District.

Methodology

For the present study, documentation method is used. That is, documenting or evaluating how much activities are going on regarding the rejuvenation of the study area. For that, secondary data is used to collect information about the activities carried around Kanampuzha River from records of local bodies and for an extent some personal discussion is also carried out to gather information.

Rejuvenation Programme

River rejuvenation is an effort aimed at restoring the poor health of overexploited and polluted rivers. It requires an understanding of the causes for the poor health and the restoration efforts from source to sink (ICFR 2014). Depending on the level of deterioration, river rejuvenation aims at a new sustainable, healthy river ecosystem. It can be achieved by restoring the river health to an accepted historical state. Avoiding direct entry of domestic sewage and industrial effluents into river certainly improve the river health. The flow of a river is its identity and the most significant variable of a river system. Besides performing various functions, it gives self-cleaning and healing powers. Thus, the river rejuvenation broadly calls for optimal water flow through the river system during different seasons. It can be achieved by ensuring environmental flow in the river. Sinha et al. (2013) also emphasize on the estimation of river recovery potential and path along with threshold conditions for sustainable management of the river systems in the Ganga River basin. The concept of environmental flow in river management applied in some or other form in 72 countries around the world IWMI (2005). For that measures based on the understanding of river ecosystem coupled with environmental flow should be integrate in to the river rejuvenation efforts.

With an ambitious project by the Kerala government in association of the Haritha Mission bring a new life to the dying rivers. This integrates waste management, organic farming, and water resources rejuvenation in the state.

The project will primarily aim to clear up blocked rivers, canals, rivulets and local ponds in several districts to allow the free flow of water.

The Executive Vice-Chairperson of the Haritha Kerala Mission, T N Seema said, it will arrange training, and technical motivation to three layers of local self governments who is ready to undertake rejuvenation projects. And ensured the co-operation of other related government department like irrigation.

The revival process includes selection of all water bodies, and apart from cleaning up the river beds, and de-weeding, increase water body's depth will also undertake, and will boost the river flow there by fill the nearby dried-up channels.

Regarding resource mobilization for the project, the Varattar model was followed by the Mission, which saw active public participation regarding funding. Other rejuvenation projects of the Mission like campaigning, and mobilization, it successfully used Public participation, and will be the facilitating platform for combined work of the people and departments.

The plan for integration of the Pallikalar, Kolarayar and Meenachilar rivulets flowing through the Kollam and Pathanamthitta, and Kannur's Kanampuzha have been fixed initially. Many agricultural lands were lying fallow due to the dried up conditions of canals running around the fields. The rejuvenation projects, a noticeable improvement in paddy cultivation with the rebirth of water bodies.

Kananmpuzha River

The Kananmpuzha river of the Kannur district originating from Ayyappanmala at Mundry Panchayath, and flows through various areas such as Elayavoor, Thazhe Chovva, and Kannur corporation limits. It is a main water source has traditionally recharged groundwater across all the catchement it flows.

But over the last few years, people began to use it as a dumping yard of their solid and liquid waste. The river filled with soil from the nearby farms and coastal communities become totally spoiled by the wastes. It destructed the life on the banks of the river as well as agriculture. But through the rejuvenation of river programme by the State Government, the river has undergone a favorable makeover with the help of local people's participation.

The Haritha Keralam Mission initiated by the government of Kerala undertook a cleaning programme throughout the state by cleaning water bodies, and soil on December, 2016. Through waste management, organic farming and conservation of water resources with people's support, the Mission tried to clean and green the state. The cleaning was undertaken along a 10 Km stretch from Chelora panchayat to

Marakkarkandy in Kannur Corporation and removed all plastics and other wastes. The committee set up for cleaning purpose also decided to devote one day in a month to maintain the cleaning activities of the river and made a suggestion that they will check the waste emission activities on this river. Through Haritha Kerala Mission, administration and local communities are go hand-in-hand to undertake varieties of developmental programmes including reclaiming lands for agriculture, waste segregation, and recycling of wastes in panchayats, and municipalities. It is a citizen-driven initiative. The primary agenda of the Mission has been water conservation and through their activities, Kanampuzha got a new lease of life and step towards a sustainable future.

A tiny river is passing through Kannur Assembly Constituency; Kanampuzha was giving a new lease of life with the efforts of the people who took it on a mission mood on May 15th, 2018 and the river cleaned by more than 5000 people. Finance Minister of Kerala, Dr. Thomas Isaac inaugurated the function. And he said that the government is formulating a plan to reclaim the water resources in the state and fund is not a constraint for such projects and a master plan would be prepared for the purpose.

Conclusion

From the analysis, it can conclude that the rejuvenation of water bodies plays an important role in sustainable development. If we are using these water bodies for dumping our waste, definitely it will lead to the death of water bodies, and it will bring severe consequences to not only to the coming generation but the present one itself faces severe problem of water scarcity, deteriorating aquatic ecosystem, drying of nearby lands and poor performance of agriculture, etc. At present we need an environmentally sustainable development of river resource. A process-based understanding of the river ecosystem will facilitate sustainable exploitation of water resource. So that humanity can enjoy the river ecosystem benefits for several generations. The environmental flow concept helps us in deciding the sustainable limits to river resource development. In the case of the river system in poor river health, river rejuvenation can also be achieved by broadly aiming at restoring assured environmental flow in the river system. The planners and policymakers should necessarily integrate this concept with water resources development strategy.

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